

THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF SOFTWARE-METHODICAL COMPLEXES IN INCREASING EDUCATIONAL EFFICIENCY

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Annotation: *This article discusses the role of software-methodical complexes in the modern education system, their importance in increasing educational efficiency and their integration with information technologies. It also covers the structural structure of such complexes, their impact on the educational process and the possibilities of their application in practice.*

Keywords: *software-methodical complex, information technologies, e-learning, educational efficiency, electronic textbook, multimedia, interactive education.*

TA'LIM SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA DASTURIY – METODIK MAJMUALARNING O'RNI VA AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya: *Mazkur maqolada zamonaviy ta'lim tizimida dasturiy-metodik majmualarning o'rni, ularning ta'lim samaradorligini oshirishdagi ahamiyati va axborot texnologiyalari bilan integratsiyasi haqida fikr yuritilgan. Shuningdek, bunday majmualarning tarkibiy tuzilmasi, ta'lim jarayoniga ta'siri va ularni amaliyotga tadbiq etish imkoniyatlari yoritilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *dasturiy-metodik majmua, axborot texnologiyalari, elektron ta'lim, ta'lim samaradorligi, elektron darslik, multimedia, interaktiv ta'lim.*

РОЛЬ И ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ПРОГРАММНО-МЕТОДИЧЕСКИХ КОМПЛЕКСОВ В ПОВЫШЕНИИ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

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***Аннотация:** В данной статье рассматривается роль программно-методических комплексов в современной системе образования, их значение в повышении эффективности образования и интеграция с информационными технологиями. Также рассматриваются структурная структура таких комплексов, их влияние на образовательный процесс и возможности их применения на практике.*

***Ключевые слова:** программно-методический комплекс, информационные технологии, электронное обучение, эффективность обучения, электронный учебник, мультимедиа, интерактивное обучение.*

In recent years, much attention has been paid to the issue of organizing the educational process on the basis of information technologies, in particular computers, since the use of modern educational technologies in the educational process gives a highly positive effect. Forming the educational process on the basis of computers and information technologies, whether in the humanities (history, philosophy, literature, etc.) or in the natural sciences (mathematics, physics, chemistry, etc.), equips the teacher, on the one hand, and the student, on the other, with a powerful tool, the full capabilities of which have not yet been revealed. In particular, if the teacher has the opportunity to rely on a software and methodological complex that includes audio and video clips to increase the efficiency of preparing lecture texts, handouts, tasks for practical exercises, recommendations on seminar and independent work topics, and audio and video clips to enhance the mastery of topics, students will have the opportunity to deeply understand the theory, solve more and more examples in practical exercises, be active in seminars, visualize their presentations, and most importantly, independently discover new knowledge.

Software and methodological complexes created on the basis of information technologies not only increase the effectiveness of the educational process, but also open up wide opportunities for the use of new teaching methods in it. The possibility of presenting existing educational materials in a figurative form based on information technologies such as multimedia and platforms, the representation of information not as simple text, but through images, and the description of topics through mathematical constructions and algorithms, as well as the presentation of each topic through video lessons in several languages, indicate that information technologies occupy a special place in the educational system.

Ensuring the timely development and introduction of modern pedagogical and information technologies, as well as providing the material and technical base of educational institutions with new educational literature, modern equipment and computer technology, and introducing educational and methodological complexes,

software and methodological complexes and information technologies into the educational process are among the most urgent tasks of the system.

The main content of the electronic education system is software and methodological complexes (the word content in English means "content" - that is, "text file", "audio file", "multimedia files and their complements").

Naturally, the use of software and methodological complexes in education, their introduction into the educational process requires the implementation of a number of changes and reforms in the field of educational and methodological support, that is, the development of the intellectual base of education, and increasing the effectiveness of training.

It is logical that the content of program-methodical complexes for a specific subject consists of the following categories:

a) Traditional educational-methodical complex for the subject:

- Details of mandatory knowledge and skills in the corresponding state educational standard;
- Curriculum for the specialty;
- Work program;
- Model program.

b) Innovative component:

- Methodological principles aimed at increasing student activity and proven in practice, methodological complexes, visual aids and software appropriate to them;
- Methodological tasks for independent studies;
- Methodological developments for computer practice in the subject;
- A set of test tasks that determine the quality of mastered knowledge in the subject;
- Experimentation and implementation of mathematical constructions, algorithms, block diagrams, solutions in the MathCAD and Maple system programs and solutions in the Python programming environment;
- Conducting ratings among students on completed activities in order to increase learning efficiency;
- Surveys and methodological developments for monitoring the quality of the educational process.

c) Educational and methodological materials in electronic form:

- Electronic textbooks or textbooks;
- Electronic study guides;
- Electronic lecture texts;
- Electronic practical exercises texts;
- Special video materials;
- Electronic presentation materials;
- Interactive training courses;

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Mathematical constructions of problems for conducting computational experiments, algorithms, block diagrams, solutions in the MathCAD and Maple system programs and texts of solutions in the Python programming environment.

Educational materials are important in increasing the efficiency of the educational process in teaching with software and methodological complexes. Therefore, in this process, it is necessary to create electronic textbooks that are convenient in all respects, have graphics, multimedia and interactivity features.

Conclusion

Programmatic and methodological complexes have great potential in the education system, they serve as an important tool for improving the quality of education, enriching the educational process with modern technologies, and activating the activities of pupils and students. Therefore, their creation, development, and introduction into the educational process should be recognized as an urgent task.

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